

The European Nanotechnology Community Informatics Platform: Bridging data and disciplinary gaps for industry and regulators

Grant Agreement No 731032

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Summary

This deliverable presents specifications of training needs established by the NanoCommons consortium, based on previous projects (like FP7 [NanoEIS](#)) and on the experiences of the consortium members, to support the NanoCommons nanoinformatics community. Unlike previous educational efforts which addressed experimental approaches and principles, NanoCommons is focused primarily on data management, and data exploitation via nanoinformatics tools and models to extract additional knowledge from large datasets, and training to support users in these aspects. The specific issues laid down in the DoA were further refined and a priority ranking was performed. This deliverable considers different training users and training formats, which allows establishment of a list of training priorities. Decisions are reached concerning which user group shall be targeted first and which training formats will be developed first.

For user groups, researchers (including industry / consultancy-based researchers) will be targeted first, followed by regulators. Train-the-trainer events will be performed in later stages of the project. University undergraduate students are not seen as a priority user group at the present time, although as NanoCommons tools become increasingly widely accepted and require less and less input from the developers, teaching materials for researchers may be adapted for use in undergraduate curricula.

Regarding training forms, we will first set up a platform for existing online-based training tools. Physical trainings will be performed as soon as possible, and will be widely advertised via the NanoCommons website and linked to the calls for Transnational Access (TA). Online and physical trainings will be closely linked and will be structured in training modules. For online based training, different forms will be merged, as known from Massive Open Online Courses (MOOC). Microlearning may be explored, while print materials are considered by the consortium to be not important given the focus of the training on data management via online laboratory notebooks and on online tools for data processing, visualization and modelling.

The first training activities will be the basis for diversified training actions later in the project, when we aim at addressing different user groups and different skill levels. We also present considerations on how to work towards sustainable training offers after the lifetime of the project. Based on the present deliverable, NanoCommons will proceed to implement training activities in order of their urgency and their feasibility within a limited time.

Revision 01 of this Deliverable Report includes a detailed plan of the first training tools that are being offered, as per the recommendation from the project review meeting.

List of abbreviations

DoA	Description of Action
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
JRA	Joint Research Activities
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
NA	Networking Activities
Q&A	Question and Answer
TA	Transnational Access
WP	Work package

Introduction

In order to use the data management and nanoinformatics tools developed by NanoCommons, sufficient training is necessary. The problem is that this statement differentiates into a wide variety of individual training needs, which cannot be addressed by a fixed training package. The issue will be solved by a training landscape surrounding the NanoCommons nanoinformatics tools, where all users can find training resources and materials that are suitable for them and their needs. In order to keep the system manageable, this training landscape needs to consist of a limited number of interacting modules that can be maintained beyond the lifetime of the project. This consideration, as well as time and budget limitations, prevent setting up just a sequence of physical courses to cover training needs. While physical courses will play an important role, via Hakathons and other hands-on activities, the main activity in the long run will have to be online offers, of which numerous varieties can be imagined.

The present report gives an overview about which stakeholders we will address with our NanoCommons training offers and in which forms this shall be done. While all stakeholders are important and all forms of training have their merits, we need to decide in which order the different stakeholders will be addressed and which forms of training shall be used for these first training offers. Our considerations on these issues, the approaches we utilized when undertaking the prioritization exercise, and the conclusions we have reached are reported below.

1. User groups

We identified for the NanoCommons tools the following user groups:

- 1) **Researchers at academic institutions:** The NanoCommons project addresses nanotechnology informatics, which is a subject that in practice mainly researchers (data and hypothesis generators) have to master. This covers experts from different areas of materials sciences, chemistry, biosciences, informatics, data science, etc., but the interdisciplinarity of the field implies that it should be possible to reach them all with the same training efforts, if they are set up broad enough and with a clear view on practical applications, and with hands-on training sessions for select groups of priority users (e.g. EU-funded nanosafety projects). Note that this group also includes PhD students, who produce many data. The trainings thus have to consider the needs and experience level of Early Stage Researchers.
- 2) **Researchers at companies:** The same aspects apply for researchers at academic institutions, but some differences in backgrounds and interests can be anticipated. For example, many academics would be interested in options to include new knowledge into teaching, while industrial researchers are more likely to require links to other regulatory fields not pertaining to nanomaterials. In addition, trainings will have to fit into internal training and lifelong learning programs (e.g. Continuous Professional Development) that are arranged within companies.
- 3) **People from regulatory agencies:** NanoCommons aims to help close the gap between researchers and regulators. Regulators don't need to feed data into nanoinformatics tools, but they need to fully understand and operate these tools, understand their Domains of applicability, their limitations and their comparative advantages relative to other tools / approaches. It is necessary to get an agreement between both groups on using NanoCommons tools to facilitate their interactions and to speed up the transition to *in silico* nanosafety risk assessment. Trainings of regulators should therefore take place during the project, in order to enable a meaningful dialogue.
- 4) **Administrators:** Administrators will normally not use nanoinformatics tools, but they need to understand the functions and outputs of tools well enough to agree to their use. In addition, administrators are in a position to approve training for their staff. Training will here be in form of information packages that allow administrators to reach informed decisions regarding adoption of the tools / training packages.
- 5) **University students:** This group can use NanoCommons tools only to a limited extent. If we ignore work performed during a PhD thesis (see group 1), we can anticipate, however, that tools will be applied in academic training courses. While this does not directly contribute to scientific output, it is efficient to familiarize a larger number of future experts with concepts and solutions relating to nanoinformatics and data management broadly. A modification of existing training materials could allow the project to also reach this user group, which is relevant for the long-term adoption of NanoCommons concepts and tools.

All of these user groups are important, but it has to be decided which ones shall be targeted first. The partners have discussed this question at length (a survey used in that process is included as annex 1), coming to the conclusion that **active researchers will be targeted first**, since this group also constitute the main users of the TA component of NanoCommons and as such will be early adopters of the NanoCommons tools and approaches. The question as to whether academic or industrial scientists should be the first group to aim for could not be satisfactorily answered. We will thus aim with our first trainings at researchers in general, irrespective of where they are based. Later on, courses may be differentiated between the two subgroups, supported by feedbacks on trainings offered by the first rounds of participants. Similarly, training for the other user groups will be differentiated later on. We need to ensure that regulators are fully in agreement with our efforts, so this group could be the next one to be targeted. This will also be achieved via other Networking activities (NA) within NanoCommons such as the community building and stakeholder feedback sessions (NA1), and the demonstration regulatory dossiers (for example) and case studies (NA3).

Figure 1. User groups of NanoCommons services as anticipated by the members of the NanoCommons consortium.

2. Training formats

2.1 General considerations

The most obvious distinction regarding training formats is between physical and online formats. Both have their advantages and shall be used to various degrees. We distinguish five types of training formats, which are:

- **Physical meetings, training on site:** A highly efficient form of training, as direct learning from experts is in many aspects the best way. However, the drawbacks are obvious as well: On-site meetings are available only for a limited number of people and they exclude those that cannot participate for time or financial reasons. They are also the most difficult training activity to keep up after the end of the project. Still, physical meetings, for example hackathons using training datasets and case studies combined with online tools are excellent trainings, which will be set up as soon as possible. Indeed, the first Hakathon was held immediately after the 2nd NanoCommons general Assembly in Athens on 9th October 2018, addressing Ontological Annotation of Data Sets, with 2 more planned for each of the next 3 years (see also Appendix C, MS9 Report).
- **Internet training courses with online trainers:** This form of training solves problems of travel costs and of on-site organization. It can accommodate more people, but within limits: There should be time for every participant to interact with the trainer (or trainers). It is easier to keep up than on site trainings, but still requires considerable efforts. Persons taking care of an interactive online course translate into personnel costs. Two online Hackathons on the Ontological Annotation of Data Sets are planned for late 2018 – one with the Centre for Sustainable Nanoscience led by the University of Wisconsin, and one with King Mongkut's University of Technology Thonburi (KMUTT), Thailand for senior and young scientists. Based on these, an optimized set of training materials will be available, that can be utilized for self-study also (see below).
- **Internet training courses for self-studies:** Such trainings can be taken any time and nearly any place. They can be directly linked to the NanoCommons tools, so if there is a problem with a certain challenge, users can be directed to a training module that addresses this aspect. Participation is unlimited and, if desired, can be free of charge. This type of tools takes substantial effort to set up, since it is necessary to anticipate all realistic user problems. The disadvantage is obvious: If a user encounters a problem and there is no further help feature, the user is stuck. A help desk could be considered, which would have to be maintained in the long run. Indeed, the NanoCommons help-desk for TA users could be utilized to provide real-time support for questions that emerge during self-study, which would also support the refinement of the training materials, and the development of the Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) supporting materials for TA and Training.
- **Printed materials:** While being old-fashioned, print materials still have their uses. A printed manual or book could be a valuable help for users. Such an item could be provided as printed book or as a pdf-file.
- **Train-the-trainer events:** Training future trainers will always require hybrid forms of training. The effort here is the highest, but it is essential to maintain impact after the end of the project. This issue is discussed in section 2.3.

Both physical and internet-based trainings have their supporters in the consortium. It was decided to **first move ahead with internet-based trainings**. A substantial amount of training material is already available in the consortium, while other topics are well covered by existing online resources. Internet-based training modules can therefore be set up rather quickly, so they will be the first tools to be implemented. **A platform for online training offers will be established on the project website**. This does not imply that all materials are to be hosted there, since in the case of already existing offers, a link to the relevant resource may be sufficient. **The NanoCommons website will provide a clear guide for potential users where training tools can be found, what competences would be expected at the start of the training, how much time they should dedicate and which competences they can expect to acquire as a result of participating in the training**. In terms of curation activities specifically, the consortium is working on development of a certification for research data curation, specifically for nano, but also more generally.

Physical trainings will be performed within the project. They will be interlinked with online training offers, which will complement the on-site events. In the end, both training types will help to improve each other by providing materials and user feedback. The physical meeting will to some extent be a hybrid format, since online training materials and hands-on elements will be centrally integrated. Besides being good practice for users, this is also the best way to identify gaps in the online training offers: Users can give immediate input and feedback. Such information will be used for improvements and refinements of the training tools, and will feed into the certification for research data curation.

Print materials are not seen as central to the project, so no specific action of this type is planned. The whole question of training formats will be re-evaluated throughout the project. In particular, we will reconsider these issues during the project meetings, based on user and stakeholder feedback from all aspects of the project (NA and TA activities).

The different forms of online trainings are discussed in the next section.

2.2 Types of internet based learning

Internet based training can come in many forms. The major formats that could be applied for NanoCommons training purposes are:

- **Videos:** This is an old-fashioned tool, but it continues to be important. The success of YouTube shows that videos are still very effective for transporting knowledge. It is expected that users will readily use this format, so there is nearly no barrier. This is, for the purposes of NanoCommons, a good format, where for example features of a tool can be explained by showing the relevant screen, while a voice-over explains what is going on. An additional advantage is that it would be easy to produce versions in different languages.
- **Interactive webinars:** They are listed here to represent in general online training formats, in which people interact online. The main advantage is that users can ask questions and can present their own user cases. Users can interact with each other, for example when exercises and other forms of homework are distributed to groups of participants. This format can be considered as highly efficient, and if it is followed by an examination it leaves the option to hand out certificates, or with a data-upload for example to assess what worked and what didn't. However, there is a significant

input of person hours and of course, interactive webinars can only be offered at certain fixed times.

- **Q&A sessions with a training program (not a living person):** This format allows the user to interact with the program. Users can answer questions and find out whether their answer is correct, or, even more importantly, why their answer is wrong. They can also be challenged to solve more complex questions for training scenarios. A disadvantage is that the barrier to participate is higher, but on the other hand the success of training can be readily assessed by the user (and by the training developer based on the amount of time spent by users on specific sections and what they got right/wrong). Of note, interactive online formats are a form of training that does not require a trainer, but is still able to implement grading and certification. Tests can be integrated into the program, so there is information on user performance and successful completion can be easily verified. This type of training is accepted for example for training in lab safety prior to undertaking laboratory experiments.
- **Full internet courses for self-training:** This can take many shapes, none of which require interaction with a trainer, so they can be taken anytime. Videos and training programs can be part of it, but full courses aim to be comprehensive. It would be expected to blend different forms of learning, which can be a challenge, because with higher ambitions it gets more difficult to set up such a course. In addition, an extensive training program may overshoot user needs. If a training course gets too extensive, it may also not fit into our concept of training via a number of modules.
- **Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs):** The MOOC format aims to reach as many people as possible and is free of charge. MOOCs were originally based on existing lecture series that were provided via the internet as videos and with accompanying materials. Later on, MOOCs were also developed from scratch, making creative use of internet tools like social media and wikis. There is no interaction between teachers and students, as some courses reach hundreds of thousands of participants. We don't expect a truly massive interest in our tools, but elements of MOOCs could be productively integrated. For example, the lack of teacher oversight in a MOOC can be countered by facilitating user groups where users discuss content, work together on scenarios and grade each other's solutions, or in the context of the recent Hakathons on dataset annotation, could discuss what ontological terms they chose to assign to a specific physico-chemical or toxicological endpoint.
- **Microlearning:** This is the first training format that really takes the smartphone into account. Learning is in small packages, like brief notes, information snippets and quizzes¹. Users can work anytime and for as long as they like: Typically, just a few minutes are spent. Quizzes provide a good feedback to the user about the success of the training. This format can certainly cover only a part of the knowledge needs, but it is an excellent tool for learning facts. A downside is that microlearning cannot be implemented by the any of the current consortium partners, so a third party like a commercial supplier would be required.

Some training materials related to the NanoCommons tools are already online from previous projects (e.g. [eNanoMapper](#), [NanoMILE](#)). They will be the basis for the NanoCommons training landscape. ***The first task is to provide on the project website a full documentation of existing trainings and to set up a single entry point for users looking for training options.*** Training videos will likely be the first new elements to be included in this training platform. At the end of the project, the training platform will be comprehensive and it will be possible to update it with limited effort. In this way, the NanoCommons tools will be enabled for all interested users in the future.

Online training tools need to be developed and integrated into the final NanoCommons models and tools package. **Webinars will be performed within the project** and they will be used to improve online tools based on user feedback. Training tools will integrate videos and elements from MOOCs, like options for a training user community. They will provide training data sets and allow users to solve specific exercises, guided by the program. Extending and modifying this basic toolbox will allow set-up of online training for different user groups, enable provision of online materials that can be used in physical and hybrid courses and connection of parts of it to different training platforms. Training e.g. in applied informatics or in general toxicology, for example, could benefit from instruments developed in NanoCommons. Based on our experiences we will improve training materials within the project. **As NanoCommons tools become published on the website, they will be complemented by training offers for self-study.** Based on these materials, we will also offer **information packages about NanoCommons tools for non-experts**, like administrators, but maybe also other groups, like media and general public.

In order to achieve these goals, it is necessary that **the entire training landscape is structured in a modular way.** Individual modules, which can have different components, need to address defined issues without unnecessary overlaps. The modules will be linked to each other, so users are directed straight to additional or advanced modules that could be interesting to them. Modules can also share elements. For example, it can be useful to include a brief general introduction in each module, which can be skipped by experienced users. The platform linking all modules will also contain an overall Q&A section and a guide for further studies that go beyond the scope of the NanoCommons tools, but could be useful for users (for example, participants in our research data curation training may be interested to progress to masters level courses in library or museum curation).

Microlearning is an interesting approach and we will explore options to use this method. No budget for a commercial supplier is anticipated in the project, but our efforts can be useful to guide future projects and other parties interested in nanosafety.

2.3 Train the trainer

Training people who act as educators and multipliers after the end of the project is essential to its sustainability. **Train-the-trainer events need to be physical meetings** and they need to go through a number of applications of a given tool. This type of training is intensive in terms of time and effort, but allows the trainers to then go back to their institutes / countries and offer the training there – this will be especially important in terms of targeting users in new member states and Associated countries, which traditionally have quite low uptake of tools and services and TA.

Train-the-trainer events will be tailored to the persons taking part, for example by using user cases provided by the trainees. The goal is to have at the end of the NanoCommons project a sufficient number of senior users for each tool, who are essentially as familiar with the tool as the people who created them. These people are the trainers for the future and they will also play an important role in raising awareness and promoting community as well as industry and regulatory adoption of the NanoCommons tools and models.

For train-the-trainer events, the tools should be essentially in their final form. These events will therefore be performed towards the end of the project. It will be decided later on how to select attendees, but a sizable number will be encouraged to be from new member states and associated countries, to encourage their participation. We expect that they will include persons from partners, from other

ongoing EU projects and from additional interested parties also. To what extent trainees will be recruited by invitation and by application will be discussed later.

2.4 Conclusions on training formats

Physical meetings, trainer-guided online formats and self-guided online formats will all be applied as means to train the research community in the use of the NanoCommons tools and models. Additional formats may be used as well, as discussed above. The training activity needs to start somewhere. This starting point will be **1) non-interactive online training formats**. The reason is that these formats – which partially already exist – can be set up fast and with almost immediate effect. They will **2) next be complemented by videos** which are linked to the tools. **3) Third in line will be physical training events**. These latter events will, in turn, be the basis for **4) webinars and other forms of interactive web-based teaching**, which will to some extent be an approximation to a physical course, so it is practical to do physical trainings first and base online formats on the experiences made with them.

Our decisions concerning the anticipated sequence of training formats are pragmatic. We start with what is quickest to realize and build from there. The sequence of introduction does not imply a ranking of importance. While the consortium has discussed the merits of different formats, it will in the end be the users who decide by preferring different information sources to others, a process that will be monitored throughout the project based on the use of Google Analytics and other means to track user engagement and duration spent interacting with the different training materials.

Figure 2. Training formats for NanoCommons services as anticipated by the members of the NanoCommons consortium most suitable for the user groups identified.

3. NanoCommons Training content

The training content has to be aligned to the nanoinformatics and data management tools that are developed, so the scientific content can be considered to be pre-defined. However, some general standards regarding content can be noted:

- The training tool defines clearly which skills will be acquired by using it. There is, therefore, a clear understanding about training goals.
- There are detailed links to the tool that is addressed, and a step-by-step guide to utilizing the tool – uploading data, applying the tool and in principle, to interpreting the data generated utilizing the tool or model.
- There are also links to other information sources, both within the NanoCommons platform and outside of it. Specifically, there will also be guidance on pre-requisites and follow-on content to direct users to other related and relevant tools.
- It is explained what the tool can do, and, more importantly, what it cannot do. This also includes details of the limitations, the domain of applicability of the model and whether the prediction produced from the tool is robust. This is important for preventing non-appropriate use, which would lead to erroneous conclusions. Contact details for the tool developers and the help-desk will also be provided to facilitate self-learners / independent users to check that their interpretation is correct.

4. First training tools planned

Table 1 below lists the training tools for NanoCommons' transnational access (TA) services which shall become available online first (grouped in TA service categories):

TA service category	Training tool	Format	Level
Experimental workflow	PC characterization protocols	Written tutorial	Basic
Data processing/analysis	Biomax data templates	Recorded webinar	Basic
	NIKC data templates	Written tutorial	Advanced
	Jaqpot platform	Video	Advanced
		Video	Expert
	Enalos NanoXtract for TEM	Video	Basic
		Online tutorial	Basic
Openrisknet e-infrastructure	Online webinar incl video	Basic	
	Online webinar incl video and documentation	Advanced	
Data visualization/toxicity prediction	Enalos cloud for zeta potential	Video	Basic
		Online webinar	Basic
	Enalos cloud for Safe-by-Design	Video	Basic
		Online tutorial	Basic
Guidenano	Series of online webinars	Intro - Basic - Advanced	
Data storage	Scinote	Video	Basic
		Online tutorial	Basic
	ACEnano knowledge infrastructure	Online tutorial	Basic

For each of the training tools the expected level of expertise shall be indicated, the training goals shall be identified. The training tools will be made available through the NanoCommons infrastructure webpace (<https://infrastructure.nanocommons.eu/>). The list of online available training tools will be presented at several scientific and stakeholder meetings for promoting its use.

5. Final remarks

This report contributes to task 8:1 - Establishment of Training Needs:

“This task will establish the training needs in the community and develop the prospective NanoCommons training program. Existing training instruments will be surveyed and this information used to identify a suitable training portfolio and information toolbox that will both be made accessible via the NanoCommons online platform (provided via JRA2).

The training program to be developed will seek to encompass knowledge management tools, workflows, ontologies and computational tools, for which content and suitable User groups are defined. In those cases where specific training gaps are identified resources will be given to assessing the feasibility of developing new training materials.”

The present report describes the rationale of actions to be taken in the near future and explains why we have decided on a specific sequence of events for implementing the NanoCommons training landscape. Given the informatics focus of NanoCommons, priority has been given to online resources and Hackathon type hands-on training events, including remotely run Hackathons.

We will assess with users of the first training events how important it is to provide a certification for training activities. We will also discuss what type of certificate would be needed, e.g. a certificate from an external institution vs. one given by the existing consortium, and indeed are working on development of an externally validated certification for research data curation, identified as a major gap in current training, and an incentive for researchers to undertake curation of their datasets. User feedback is in general important to shape the future training landscape, so we gain insights from third parties, which will ensure that the training offers are aligned with evolving and emerging user needs.

6. References

1. <https://elearning.adobe.com/2018/04/5-killer-microlearning-examples-employee-training/>

Appendixes

Appendix A: Internal survey on training

Survey on Training, WP8

Reponse from (person): _____

Reponse from (partner): _____

Q1: For which **stakeholders** are training offers by NanoCommons most important?
Please assign numbers 1-5 to the following stakeholder groups in order of importance, 1 indicating the most urgent need, 5 the least.

- A1:
- | | |
|---|---|
| Researchers at companies | — |
| Administrators at companies | — |
| People at regulatory agencies | — |
| Researchers at universities or institutes | — |
| University students | — |

Q2: How **useful** are different forms of training in your field within NanoCommons? Rate by numbers. 1 = essential; 2 = particularly useful; 3 = useful; 4 = nice to have; 5 = irrelevant

- A2:
- | | |
|--|---|
| Physical meetings, training on site | — |
| Internet training courses with online trainers | — |
| Internet training courses for self-studies | — |
| Printed materials | — |
| Train-the-trainer events | — |

Q3: Can you **contribute** already existing training tools, or point out existing tools that would be particularly useful for integrating them in the NanoCommons training plan? Give links if possible.

A3: _____

Q4: Are you willing to help **define** training contents for our training activities? Which ones?

A4: _____

Q5: Going back to the internet based training; there are many different ways to perform this. Examples include

- Videos
- Webinars
- Q & A sessions with a training program (not a living person)
- Full internet course for self-training (formerly often provided as CDs)
- Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs)
- Microlearning
- Internet tools combined with a physical course

MOOCs can be based on an existing lecture or training to which e.g. videos, quizzes and discussion boards for participants are added. They can also be set up from scratch, typically with a strong interactive aspect. Note that this does not allow training beyond the lifetime of the project.

Microlearning is learning in small steps, typically used on smartphones. The user can learn everywhere and can stop whenever wanted.

Having considered this, which internet tools should we focus on?

A5: _____

Appendix B: Answers to questions in the survey by NanoCommons partners

Eight partner representatives answered the survey. The ranking assigned by these regarding the importance of stakeholders and usefulness of tools are indicated below. For Question 5, the answers received are listed.

Q1: For which **stakeholders** are training offers by NanoCommons most important?

Please assign numbers 1-5 to the following stakeholder groups in order of importance, 1 indicating the most urgent need, 5 the least.

A1: Researchers at companies	2, 2, 2, 1, 1, 3, 1, 1
Administrators at companies	5, 4, 4, 1, 4, 5, 5, 5
People at regulatory agencies	3, 1, 3, 2, 2, 2, 2, 4
Researchers at universities or institutes	1, 3, 1, 1, 4, 1, 3, 2
University students	4, 4, 5, 2, 5, 4, 4, 3

Q2: How **useful** are different forms of training in your field within NanoCommons? Rate by numbers. 1 = essential; 2 = particularly useful; 3 = useful; 4 = nice to have; 5 = irrelevant

A2: Physical meetings, training on site	2, 1, 2, 2, 1, 1, 1, 4
Internet training courses with online trainers	1, 3, 1, 2, 4, 1, 4, 1
Internet training courses for self-studies	3, 4, 3, 1, 5, 2, 5, 3
Printed materials	4, 5, 4, 4, 3, 3, 3, 3
Train-the-trainer events	3, 2, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 2

Q5: Going back to the internet based training; there are many different ways to perform this. Examples include

- Videos
- Webinars
- Q & A sessions with a training program (not a living person)
- Full internet course for self-training (formerly often provided as CDs)
- Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs)
- Microlearning
- Internet tools combined with a physical course

MOOCs can be based on an existing lecture or training to which e.g. videos, quizzes and discussion boards for participants are added. They can also be set up from scratch, typically with a strong interactive aspect. Note that this does not allow training beyond the lifetime of the project.

Microlearning is learning in small steps, typically used on smartphones. The user can learn everywhere and can stop whenever wanted.

Having considered this, which internet tools should we focus on?

Respondent A:

Videos, Webinars, Microlearning

Respondent B:

Use case based Microlearning/Videos of individual steps covering all parts, from NM characterization to model based toxicology prediction _____

Full course for in-depth description of individual parts of the use case e.g. model generation if the individual step is too complex for Microlearning/short Video

Respondent C:

Internet tools combined with a physical course

Respondent D:

Videos, Webinars, Microlearning (potentially internet tools combined with a physical course)

Respondent E:

Internet tools combined with a physical course

Respondent F:

Videos, webinars, internet tools with physical course, microlearning

Respondent G:

For the beginning, training on site could be suitable but expensive for the trainer and the trainees (travel costs). In my opinion, videos are the most appropriate solution: they are very popular, fancy, kind of cheap and easy to do (depending on the professionalism of the final video).

The idea of adding “Nanoozo” (Stacey’s sock-puppet), as “mascot” of the project, in the videos, asking the dummy questions, would be fun!

Appendix C: Milestone 9 Report

The European Nanotechnology Community Informatics Platform: Bridging data and disciplinary gaps for industry and regulators

Grant Agreement No 731032

Milestone 9

Milestone MS9 Topics & Timings for Hackathons agreed & organisation underway

Work Package WP9: NA3 - Dissemination & Case studies

Due date M6 - 30 June 2018

Lead Beneficiary NTUA

Means of verification Topics & Timings for Hackathons agreed & organisation underway
Means of verification: Rolling announcements on project website

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Description

The NanoCommons project has proposed an ambitious dissemination plan, which will ensure that the research infrastructure will reach out to the widest possible set of Users and stakeholders. An important aspect that will define to a great extent the success of the dissemination programme is training and support for Users on integrating their own data into the NanoCommons knowledge infrastructure. Towards that goal, hackathons will provide hands-on training experience to interested users (researchers, industry and regulators) on the NanoCommons tools, data formats, ontologies and user interfaces that will allow them to transfer their data into the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase, share them with the community, integrate them with other data coming from different sources and eventually search through the complete set of curated and user-input data in the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase in order to receive the most valuable and extensive information set for modelling and analysis purposes. Hackathons will also facilitate the exchange of views and will provide valuable feedback from end-users towards improvement and the much-desired convergence of NanoCommons data capturing tools and knowledge integration services. Recognising the importance of hackathons for the successful community adoption of the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase and nanoinformatics tools, and the critical role of the successful delivery of the dissemination plan in achieving this, we have proposed to plan for hackathons well in advance in order to be able to:

- Involve actively the community and especially NSC projects that would choose to schedule bespoke or project-specific workshops and training or other activities either around the NanoCommons infrastructure or by inviting the NanoCommons team to their meetings.
- Communicate efficiently and in an organized fashion the hackathon events and the procedure to request a project-specific NanoCommons hackathon in association with an NSC project meeting.
- Ensure that the events will run smoothly, be cost efficient and will produce successful outcomes and results for both NanoCommons and the NSC projects and users.

Table 1 below shows the plan of the hackathon events. Hackathons will be scheduled to run in parallel with NanoCommons or other NSC project meetings, on topics driven by implementing projects and aligning to the user needs. This is a low-cost option but at the same time it maximises the impact as it ensures that a critical mass of potential users will participate in the hackathons and that the topics remain sufficiently focused to be of maximal use to the specific user group. The hackathons will be announced on the project website, but will be additionally communicated via multiple alternative channels (NSC communications, social media, relevant nano community events) etc.

The first NanoCommons hackathon will take place in Athens in October 2018 as part of the mid-year NanoCommons meeting, and planning is already underway.

Table 1. List of proposed topics and timing for NanoCommons hackathons

Topic	Options for timing, related project or event	Location (if available)
Year 1 - 2018		
Ontological Annotation of Data Sets	Q4 (Oct, 8-9, 2018 <i>NanoCommons Mid-Year Project meeting</i>)	Athens, Greece
Year 2 - 2019		
Development of Data Capture Templates (aligned with D3.4 - M12)	Q1-Q2 (Annual meetings / conferences in NanoCommons, ACEnano, NSC) Aligned with D2.1 - 1st Annual conference & nano-exploitation day, stakeholder workshop & User call (M12)	
Development of protocols and data capture workflows (aligned with D3.2 - M12)	Q3-Q4 (OpenRiskNet final meeting, OpenTox Euro Conference)	
Year 3 - 2020		
Integration of data into NanoCommons KnowledgeBase	Q1-Q2 (Annual meetings / conferences in NanoCommons, ACEnano, NSC) Aligned with D2.5 - 2nd Annual conference & nano-exploitation day, stakeholder workshop with TA calls and demonstrations (M25)	
Experimental design and informatics workflow for risk assessment (aligned with D6.1 - M18)	Q3-Q4 (4th NanoSafety Forum for Young Scientists, ACEnano final meeting, OpenTox Euro Conference)	
Year 4 - 2021		

<p>Development of data analysis tools and predictive models based on the NanoCommons KnowledgeBase</p>	<p>Q1-Q2 <i>(Annual meetings / conferences in NanoCommons, NSC)</i></p> <p>Aligned with D2.7 - 3rd Annual conference & nano-exploitation day, social web activities, stakeholder workshop with TA calls/demonstrations (M37)</p>	
<p>Use of the decision support system(s) <i>(aligned with D6.3 - M30 and D6.4 - M36)</i></p>	<p>Q3-Q4 <i>(NanoCommons final meeting, OpenTox Euro Conference)</i></p> <p>Aligned with D2.9 - Final Annual conference & nano-exploitation Day, social web activities, stakeholder workshop, TA Demonstrations (M48)</p>	